

The Invisible City: Not All Streets Are Seen Equally

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Abstract

Street View Imagery (SVI) has become a key source of urban data for geospatial applications. With advances in machine learning and computer vision, SVI enables the extraction of insights related to urban functionality, mobility, and socioeconomic conditions. However, the temporal dimension of SVI remains largely overlooked, potentially introducing bias in downstream learning models. Using historical SVI metadata across fine-grained spatial grids in Glasgow, UK, we analyse temporal patterns of imagery updates in relation to urban infrastructure. Our results reveal a clear road-oriented bias, whereby vehicle-accessible areas are more likely to be updated and maintained more frequently than non-drivable spaces. These findings highlight the importance of jointly considering spatial and temporal coverage when using SVI as a data source for GeoAI applications.

Keywords: street view images, bias, visual information

1. Introduction

Street View Imagery (SVI) has become a key data source underpinning Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI) (Froehlich et al. 2025; Zhang and Yu 2021). Advances in computer vision have enabled SVI to support a wide range of urban analytics, including studies of human perception (Ito et al. 2024), urban greenery (Han et al. 2023), neighbourhood safety (Hamim and Ukkusuri 2024), among others (Kang et al. 2023; Fan et al. 2023; Biljecki and Ito 2021). The development of these applications has largely relied on datasets collected using default sampling strategies (Alpherts, Ghebreab, and Van Noord 2025), with an emphasis on maximising spatial coverage and reducing geographic gaps. In contrast, the temporal dimension of SVI, which is critical for capturing urban dynamism, seasonal variation, and long-term change, has received comparatively limited attention (Kim and Jang 2023; Liang, Zhao, and Biljecki 2023). As a result, machine learning models trained on SVI datasets may exhibit temporally uneven representations of the urban environment, leading to biased or unbalanced outcomes.

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In this work, we examine the temporal evenness of SVI coverage across different parts of a city, with a specific focus on how this varies across infrastructure hierarchies. Taking Glasgow, United Kingdom, as a case study, we collect historical SVI metadata from the Google Street View platform (Google 2026) and spatially align them with road-type information derived from OpenStreetMap (OSM) (OpenStreetMap contributors 2017). By analysing the city at a fine spatial resolution using regular 20 m grids (Muller et al. 2022), our results reveal a clear disparity in SVI availability between drivable and non-drivable areas. Beyond coverage, we show that SVI data recency follows a clear infrastructure hierarchy, with higher-order roads being updated substantially more frequently than lower-order or non-drivable spaces. Such bias reveals a road-oriented SVI update pattern and suggests that downstream tasks relying on SVI may disproportionately reflect vehicle-dominated urban functions and mobility contexts.

2. Method

2.1 Data

We first obtained the administrative boundary of Glasgow, UK. Within this boundary, we generated a regular set of query locations with an approximate spatial interval of 20 m, which were treated as the centres of 20 m \times 20 m sampling grids. Each query location was used to retrieve historical Google SVI panorama metadata, including panoids and their associated capture year and month. As individual panoramas can be returned for multiple nearby query locations, duplicate panoids were resolved by keeping a single record assigned to their nearest grid centre.

To characterise the local urban context, OSM data were associated with the same 20 m grid used for SVI sampling. Each grid cell was classified into a road-accessibility category (drivable, non-drivable, or no road) based on intersecting OSM road types. A primary road class was then assigned to each grid using a predefined priority order applied to all intersecting *highway* tags, ensuring that each grid was represented by the highest-order road type present within its spatial extent. The spatial grids, their associated SVI metadata, and OSM-derived contextual information were merged into a single analytical dataset.

2.2 Coverage Inequality

The analysis examines spatial and temporal patterns of SVI using the 20 m grid as the basic analytical unit. We first visualised the spatial distribution of historical SVI availability within each grid cell across Glasgow, as well as the most recent available collection date. Two complementary analytical components were then implemented to characterise SVI temporal behaviour: lifecycle-based classification of update patterns, and the distribution of data recency across the road hierarchy.

2.3 Temporal lifecycle classification

To characterise temporal updating patterns in SVI, each grid cell was classified into a lifecycle category based on the number of distinct collection dates (N_{dates}) and the maximum temporal gap between consecutive updates (Δt_{max}). Specifically, grids were categorised as: (1) Invisible

($N_{dates} = 0$); (2) One-off ($N_{dates} = 1$); (3) Forgotten ($\Delta t_{max} \geq 6$ years); and (4) Well-maintained, indicating regular updates with no gaps exceeding six years. Lifecycle categories were then aggregated by infrastructure type (drivable vs. non-drivable) to compare differences in temporal coverage and maintenance.

2.4 Recency by infrastructure hierarchy

To examine the relationship between infrastructure classification and data freshness, we analysed the distribution of SVI recency across OSM highway types, including drivable and non-drivable roads. Recency is defined as the time elapsed in months between the most recent SVI update of each grid and the latest SVI date observed across all grids. Grids were grouped by their primary highway classification and ranked in ascending order based on their median recency.

3. Sensitivity and Reproducibility

We further conducted a sensitivity analysis by varying the grid resolution from 20 m to 50 m. While the absolute median recency varies, the pattern remains consistent. In particular, the infrastructure hierarchy where major roads exhibit more recent updates than lower-order ones is preserved. Similarly, the lifecycle distribution across road types remains stable, indicating that the observed road-oriented bias is robust to grid resolution. The code of this paper is publicly available at: https://github.com/ywang-twocities/svi_fairness_glasgow_GeoAI_conference.

4. Results and Discussion

In total, 441,024 grid cells cover the study area of Glasgow. Using the centre of each grid as a query location, a total of 1,112,508 historical SVI metadata records were retrieved. Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution of the number of available dated SVI observations per grid across Glasgow. Grids with higher SVI availability are concentrated along major roads and in high-density areas such as the city centre, while availability gradually decreases towards peripheral zones. Figure 2 illustrates the most recent date on which SVI has been collected for each grid. A spatial pattern similar to the availability distribution is observed, where imageries in the city centre and along major roads are updated more recently, while many peripheral areas are temporally left behind, with imagery remaining unchanged for extended periods.

Clear differences in data lifecycle patterns emerge between drivable and non-drivable grids. As shown in Figure 3, 18% of drivable grids are completely invisible in SVI, compared to a substantially larger proportion of non-drivable grids, at 82%. In addition, the proportion of well-maintained grids in the drivable category is approximately four times higher than that of non-drivable grids, at 57% and 14% respectively. These results reveal a strong road-oriented bias in SVI coverage, with evidence that imagery is more likely to be collected and updated in areas accessible by vehicles, while pedestrian-oriented infrastructure remains under-represented.

Figure 4 further examines this temporal bias by comparing SVI recency across different road types. The results reveal a clear infrastructure hierarchy in update frequency that aligns with the functional classification of the road network. High-capacity vehicular roads, including motorways and

Count of unique year-month per 20m grid cell

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of the number of available dated Street View imagery (SVI) observations per grid across Glasgow, UK.

Most recent available Street View date per 20m grid cell

Figure 2: Most recent available SVI collection date for each grid, covering the period from 2008 to 2025.

Figure 3: Lifecycle composition of SVI across drivable and non-drivable grid cells.

primary roads, exhibit the freshest imagery, with median recency values substantially lower than the global median of 37.0 months. These road classes also show relatively narrow interquartile ranges, suggesting consistent and systematic update practices. In contrast, secondary, tertiary, and residential roads exhibit moderate update frequencies and lower-refresh patterns compared with major roads. At the lower end of the hierarchy, non-drivable and low-priority infrastructure, such as cycleways, footways, and service roads, display both older median recency values and substantially larger variances. While some segments are updated in a timely manner, large portions of pedestrian and cycling networks remain outdated.

Overall, the observed hierarchy demonstrates how SVI maintenance frequency exhibits a road-priority bias, with major vehicular corridors well-represented, while more pedestrian-oriented infrastructure is seldom updated. The findings indicate that vehicle accessibility largely governs the prioritisation of SVI updates, resulting in poor coverage or blind spots in walkable environments. The temporal and infrastructural biases have direct implications for GeoAI models that rely on SVI as a primary visual data source. Models trained on spatially and temporally imbalanced imagery are likely to learn representations that disproportionately reflect vehicle-accessible environments. Consequently, GeoAI research and applications using SVI should explicitly account for both spatial and temporal coverage, either through bias-aware training strategies, data curation, or targeted evaluation across infrastructure types. While this study focuses on Glasgow, the identified road-oriented bias is likely linked to the vehicle-based data acquisition strategy of SVI platforms, which prioritises drivable road networks. Future work will extend the proposed framework to multi-city comparative analysis.

Figure 4: Distribution of SVI recency across different road types, measured as months since the most recent update (2008–2025).

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